

Autonomous Indoor/Outdoor SAfety Tracking system

Objectives:

- High availability and integrity: Enhanced positioning and tracking system with EGNOS service
- Develop a set of tracking and alerting application protocols for fire services
- Increased safety trust of firefighters and fire chiefs
- Enabling improved fire suppression operations based on the AIOSAT system
- Reduce the impact of fires on the environment, health and economy

Concept:

The AIOSAT system will support:

- Safe team location tracking
- Increasing successful operation rates
- Avoid operation fatalities

Portable system:

- Continuous position transmit
- Data exchange and alerting system

Mobile Coordination Centre:

- Command and Control centre
- EGNOS and EDAS services enhancement for positioning
- Alerting system
- Additional communication system for coordination and information gathering

R&I activities:

- Galileo and EGNOS safety critical positioning solutions
- Indoor / outdoor positioning
- Tracking and alerting system for emergency services
- Wireless communications

Project acronym:

AIOSAT

Project title:

Autonomous Indoor/Outdoor Safety Tracking system

Project type:

Innovation Actions (IA)

Programme:

H2020-GALILEO-GSA-2017-1

Project reference:

776425

Start date:

1st December 2017

Duration:

30 months

Total cost:

€2,032,650.00

EU funding:

€1,764,262.50

Project website:

<http://www.aiosat.eu>

Project partners:

Asociacion Centro Tecnológico Ceit-IK4 (ES) (Coordinator)
 Integrasys SA (ES)
 Stichting Saxion (NL)
 Ecole Royale Militaire (BE)
 Inertia Technology B.V. (NL)
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